

Relationship between Prevalence of Microalbuminuria to Target Organ Damage in Essential Hypertensive Patients: A Hospital Based Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Age, obesity, diabetes, insulin resistance, and dyslipidemia are cardiovascular risk factors that are typically associated with essential hypertension. Early in the course of hypertension, subtle target organ damage occurs, including left ventricular hypertrophy, microalbuminuria, and cognitive impairment. We assessed the correlation between target organ damage and the occurrence of microalbuminuria in patients with essential hypertension.

Methods: 60 patients with essential hypertension in total were examined. The prevalence of albumin excretion in the urine and its relationship to damage to the target organs (stroke, retinopathy, and left ventricular hypertrophy) were examined. Microalbuminuria was measured using the urine albumin to creatinine ratio, and urinary albumin excretion was measured using the turbidimetry method.

Results: A total of 57.5% of the patients had microalbuminuria. 82.5% of patients had concomitant microalbuminuria ($p < 0.05$), and 82.82% of patients had target organ damage. Patients with longer duration and more severe cases of hypertension, elevated body mass index, and dyslipidemia were shown to have a higher prevalence among them.

Conclusion: An essential diagnostic for assessing target organ damage in hypertension individuals is the measurement of microalbuminuria. The risk of microalbuminuria is reduced by maintaining normal lipid levels, controlling weight, and managing hypertension as best as possible.

Keywords: Essential hypertension, Microalbuminuria, Target organ damage.

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Introduction

It has long been known that hypertension is a significant health burden that impacts many facets of society, especially as a major risk factor for stroke, cardiovascular disease, end-stage renal disease, and total mortality. [1] India's healthcare systems are notably and substantially impacted by hypertension (HTN). [2,3]

Different forms of Target Organ Damage (TOD) and its clinical aftereffects are linked to hypertension, even when it is asymptomatic. While catastrophic events like stroke, heart attack, renal failure, etc. are typically the result of long-term uncontrolled hypertension, subtle TOD, such as Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH), retinopathy, microalbuminuria, and cognitive dysfunction, occur early in the natural course of hypertensive disease. The majority of these patients suffer from essential hypertension, which is characterized by an increase in blood pressure that has no identified cause. Proteinuria and Microalbuminuria (MA) in hyperten-

sive adults are independent predictors of cardiovascular (CV) morbidity and mortality, according to previously available robust data. Examples of MA include urinary albumin excretion rates of 20–200 mg/min or 30-300 mg/24 hours, urinary albumin to creatinine ratios in the first voided sample in the morning greater than 30-300 mg/gm, or early morning urinary albumin concentrations of 20–200 mg/L. [4-6] Actually, the first indication of hypertensive (and diabetic) nephropathy is MA.

Furthermore, at least in the early phases, MA has been demonstrated to be reversible with ideal blood pressure and blood sugar control. [7, 8] Few researchers from this region of the world have discussed the prevalence of MA and its relationship to TOD in individuals with essential hypertension. Therefore, the present study aimed to estimate the prevalence of microalbuminuria, evaluate the likely risk factors for its development, and determine how

microalbuminuria relates to target organ damage in cases with essential hypertension.

Material and Methods

This Hospital based observational study was conducted at Department of Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar from October 2023 to September 2024. Total 60 newly detected hypertensives participants (on regular/irregular/no treatment) were included in the study. Patients with secondary hypertensive, pregnant, diabetic, acute coronary syndrome, renal disease, urinary tract infection, raised serum creatinine, macroproteinuria and smokers were excluded in this study.

Participants' informed written consent was required before data was collected using a pretested and validated proforma. Every participant had a thorough medical history taken, with particular attention paid to the length of time they had had hypertension and how it was treated, if they had ever smoked, any cardiovascular symptoms such as angina, palpitations, dyspnea, and intermittent claudication, neurological symptoms such as headache, seizures, transient ischemic attacks, and prior stroke, and visual symptoms such as blurred or diminished vision, limb weakness (hemiparesis.) etc. Previous medical history was appropriately documented, including diabetes, hypertension in first and second degree relatives, coronary heart disease, and any significant illnesses. It also documented personal history on alcohol consumption, tobacco chewing, smoking, and diet (vegetarian, non-vegetarian, and mixed). Every patient underwent a comprehensive physical examination with an emphasis on evaluating their neurological and cardiovascular conditions as well as their ocular fundus. Workup for secondary hypertension was carried out if necessary in addition to standard procedures (fasting lipid profile, ECG, chest x-ray, CT

head (if needed), 2D Echo, and albumin creatinine ratio).

Urine albumin creatinine ratio (ACR) was used to measure microalbuminuria (MA) in accordance with the American Diabetic Association and National Kidney Foundation's guidelines.(3,9) Turbidimetry was used to measure urine albumin. Five milliliters of the first voided urine sample from the morning were used. Before their urine was collected, patients were urged not to exercise. Urine tests were conducted on women during the non-menstrual part of their cycles. For the purposes of the study, microalbuminuria (MA) was defined as ACR values between 30 and 300 mg/gm of creatinine. [2]

SPSS (Version 20) was used for data analysis and chi-square test and regression analysis were performed, as indicated.

Results

60 patients with essential hypertension were assessed during the course of the current study nine months examination period. The age categories of 40-49 years and 60-69 years had the highest percentages of patients, with a mean age of 53.53 ± 12.56 years. 33 participants (55.0%) were male and 27 participants (45.0%) were female, respectively (M: F ratio: 1:0.86). The majority of patients (59.16%) reported no symptoms, but headache was the most common presenting symptom (13.33%). Newly diagnosed hypertensives made up the majority of cases (32, 53.33%) and those with hypertension for less than five years (28.33%).

Of the 60 patients with essential hypertension, 34 (56.66%) also had microalbuminuria (MA). Ageing, severe hypertension, dyslipidemia, obesity, and female gender were additional factors that markedly elevated the prevalence of MA (Table 1).

Table 1: Correlation of microalbuminuria with established risk factors

		No. of patients (n=60)	With Micoralbuminuria	Without Micoralbuminuria	p-value
Age	<60 years	38	18	19	P<0.05
	>60 years	22	16	6	
Gender	Male	33	14	19	P<0.05
	Female	27	20	6	
Blood pressure	<140/90	11	0	10	P<0.05
	Systolic 140-160 Diastolic 90-100	33	22	10	
	>160/100	16	12	5	
Dyslipidemia	Present	50	26	23	P<0.05
	Absent	10	8	2	
Obesity	Present	41	20	20	P<0.05
	Absent	19	14	5	

Duration of hypertension was found directly proportional to prevalence of MA (except for <5 years duration category) and the difference across categories was significant. Also, high prevalence was higher in patients taking on irregular or no treatment in comparison with patients on regular treatment (Table 2).

Table 2: Prevalence of microalbuminuria with respect to duration of hypertension and compliance to anti-hypertensive therapy

	No. of patients (n=60)	Micoralbuminuria present	p-value
Duration of hypertension			
Unknown duration	02(3.33%)	01(50%)	χ^2 for linear trend= 9.233, P= 0.0023
Newly diagnosed	32(53.33%)	22(68.75%)	
<5 years	17(28.33%)	05(29.41%)	
5-10 years	08(13.33%)	05(29.41%)	
>10 years	01(1.66%)	01(100%)	
Compliance to anti-hypertensive therapy			
Regular treatment	23(38.33%)	09(39.13%)	χ^2 for linear trend= 10.41, P= 0.006
No treatment	22 (36.66%)	15 (70.45%)	χ^2 for linear trend= 10.41, P= 0.006
Irregular treatment	15 (25%)	10 (66.66%)	

In 49 (81.66%) of the 60 patients with essential hypertension, target organ damage (TOD) occurred, and in 41 (82.82%) of them, microalbuminuria was present.

Microalbuminuria was discovered to be significantly correlated with target organ damage (TOD) in

the forms of stroke, retinopathy, and LVH (P=0.0072, 0.0041, and 0.001 respectively) (Table 3).

Dyslipidemia, LVH, stroke, and retinopathy remained independently correlated with MA even after multivariate analysis (Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation of microalbuminuria with target organ damage (TOD)

Target organ damage	No. of patients (n=49)	Micoralbuminuria present	p-value
Stroke	7(10.83%)	6(92.3%)	0.059
Retinopathy	25(42.5%)	18(72.54%)	0.0037
Left ventricular hypertrophy	17(29.16%)	17(94.28%)	<0.001

Discussion

60 patients with essential hypertension were included in the current study in order to investigate the prevalence of microalbuminuria (MA), potential risk factors for its occurrence, and the connection between MA and target organ damage (TOD) in these patients. MA was found to be present in 34 cases (56.66%) by the authors, which is more than what other researchers in related studies have found (6.7%-40.0%). [10,11-14] Our study participants' somewhat elevated blood pressure and the fact that the majority of patients were receiving irregular or no treatment could be the likely causes.

MA has gradually gained confirmation over time as a predictor of cardiovascular risk in those with diabetes. [15,16] One study at a time, the significance of its existence in patients of essential hypertension is now becoming clear. According to previous reports, MA was linked to advancing age, longer and more severe hypertension, obesity, and dyslipidemia; the results of this investigation support these findings. [17-19] Those with MA were far more likely to experience progressive retinal alterations (72.54%), left ventricular hypertrophy (94.28%), and stroke (92.3%). Even after multivariate analysis, retinopathy, LVH, stroke, and dyslipidemia

continued to be independently linked to MA. This suggests that hypertensives with microalbuminuria have a much higher risk of developing macrovascular and microvascular problems than those without. In the MAGIC trial, Pontremoli et al. also revealed significant associations between MA and TOD in the form of vascular retinal alterations and severe ECG abnormalities. Twelve our findings were further supported by Hitha et al., who found a similar association between the presence of MA and an increased risk of stroke and retinopathy. [12] A certain degree of correlation continuum between CV risk factors and the process from early to final renal damage is hypothesized by the presence of MA, which is thought to be the renal manifestation of generalized increased endothelial dysfunction that occurs as part of the disease process. [14,19,20]

Conclusion

MA in hypertensive subjects may be a useful marker in assessing target organ damage, and controlling risk factors that can be prevented (such as regular HT treatment, weight control, and normal lipid levels) may help prevent, postpone, and reduce the prevalence of MA. Early MA screening for hypertensive patients and timely treatment for those who

test positive could lessen the prevalence of cardiovascular and chronic renal disease in the general population.

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